

Do Firm and Board Characteristics Affect Greenhouse Gas Emission Disclosures?

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ABSTRACT: Firms in the face of climate change are expected to disclose their activities that contribute to the improvement or decrepitude of climate change. Such disclosures are referred to as GHG emission disclosures. This study investigates how board characteristics may influence the extent to which GHG emission disclosures. Board characteristics used in this study include board financial expertise, board gender diversity, board independence, board gender diversity, board meetings, and board size. The population of the study is 34 manufacturing firms listed on the Nigeria Exchange group from 2012-2021. The population of the study was chosen because manufacturing firms are one of the significant sources of GHG emissions. An ex-post facto research design was employed in this study. A purposive sampling technique was adopted to select the firms with up-to-date annual reports and sustainability reports for the study period. Secondary data for GHG emission disclosure and board characteristics were obtained from the listed Nigerian manufacturing firms' 2012–2021 annual reports and sustainability reports.

To achieve the research objectives of the study descriptive and inferential statistics were employed. The result shows that board independence {coeff. = 0.002, $p = 0.018$ }, board gender diversity {coeff. = 0.004, $p = 0.000$ }, and board financial expertise {coeff. = 0.023, $p = 0.001$ }, respectively has a positive significant effect on the GHG emission disclosure. It was revealed that board independence; board gender diversity and board financial expertise have a positive and significant effect on greenhouse gas emission disclosure. Hence, this study concluded that board characteristics affect greenhouse gas emission disclosure.

Keywords: Greenhouse Gas Emission, Gender Diversity, Financial Expertise, Independence

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1. Introduction

It is widely recognized that one of the most significant environmental issue facing the world economy is climate change, which is primarily caused by an increase in greenhouse gas (GHG) produced by human activities like the burning of fossil fuels, coal, and natural gas. Corporations have always made a substantial contribution to the issues associated with climate change, as they are among the largest emitters of GHG (Ofoegbu, Odoemelam & Okafor, 2018). Nigeria is one of the nations that contribute primarily to global greenhouse gas emissions; as of 2016, it accounted for 0.97% of all GHG emissions and this is mostly because fossil fuels are widely used in nearly all Nigerian businesses, which has a detrimental effect on people's health and quality of life. The Kyoto Protocol was created by the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC) in response to the growing concern over climate change. Nigeria approved and signed the Protocol in 2020. Furthermore, in 2016, Nigeria joined the Paris Agreement as a party and the main goal is to cut emissions by up to 20% by 2030 with both domestic and foreign support, in line with the Paris Agreement's aim to reduce the emissions of greenhouse gas. Firms have been facing pressure from various stakeholders such as consumers, governments, suppliers, investors, financial institutions, media, non-governmental organizations, and the general public to assess, reduces, and report their GHG emissions as company's activities have a significant effect on the global GHG emissions, directly or indirectly. In their respond to these pressures, firms need to play a significant role and take actions to mitigate their greenhouse gas footprint and disclose information about their greenhouse gas emissions by using various channels of communication such as greenhouse gas emission disclosure. GHG emission disclosure, which is typically included in an annual report or sustainability report, is a component of corporate social responsibility for business because it conveys the ethical values of the organization and is one way the company operates to reduce and control greenhouse gas emissions which contribute to the problem of climate change. Through GHG emission disclosure, stakeholders will assess that the company can be responsible for disseminating information about its environmental performance. However, in Nigeria, the practice of GHG emission disclosure is still carried out voluntarily and firms have developed different strategic approaches to voluntary GHG emissions disclosure which practically means that the implementation is still different in each firm. Although, not many firms are willing to disclose the GHG emissions they produce. Some firms have avoided transparency and decided not to disclose their GHG emissions while others have chosen to provide detailed information about their GHG emissions disclosure voluntarily. Firms that are willing to disclose their GHG emission are considered serious about preserving the environment as well as thinking about the impacts caused by the firm's operational activities. The majority of which are in contact with the environment and at the very least, firms that disclose GHG emissions undertake this to be in line with the legitimacy

theory. Kusumawardani and Sudana (2017), state that in legitimacy theory, firms are expected to ensure that their operations do not differ from social norms to legitimize their operations in the community. Since board characteristics are considered a valuable tool for corporate governance (CG) and could play an essential role in monitoring corporate reporting including GHG emissions disclosure practices. Several factors can influence the extent to which firms disclose their GHG emissions, including decisions, intentions, and policies in an organization. Firms in Nigeria that publicly report on their environmental performance—particularly on GHG emissions—are very rare. Thus, there is a dearth of study, particularly in developing nations like Nigeria, on the degree to which board characteristics affect the GHG emission disclosure made available by firms. Additionally, there seems to be a lack of consistency in the findings of previous research about the relationship between GHG emission disclosure and board characteristics. As a result, the disclosure of GHG emissions in this study is an interesting topic to research because environmental issues are inextricably linked to a company's operational activities, particularly for businesses that have a significant environmental impact, like those in the manufacturing, coal, oil, and gas sectors. Thus, the purpose of this study is to look into how board composition might affect how much information industrial companies listed on the Nigerian stock exchange disclose about their greenhouse gas emissions.

2. Literature Review

Conceptual Review

Greenhouse Gas Emission Disclosure

Greenhouse Gas emissions are described as gases containing greenhouse gas that are typically produced during combustion and released into the atmosphere of the Earth (Lutfiana, Bunga, & Yosefa, 2021). Human activities like aircraft, the burning of fossil fuels, deforestation, and the growth of industries all contribute to GHG emissions. GHG emissions from time to time have continued to increase both in the global, regional, national state, or local an area, and this is happening because of the growing use of energy from organic materials (fossil), land use change, and forest fires, as well as the increase anthropogenic (Pratiwi, 2016). The firms' operational activities are one factor that contributes to the greenhouse gas footprint. Businesses facing climate change are required to reveal the actions they take to mitigate the effects of climate change. GHG emission disclosures are the name given to these kinds of statements. Firms' GHG emission disclosures include the community environment, business environment, and government pressuring the firms to respond to the threats of environmental sustainability resulting from the effects of extreme climate changes (Mohammad, Aisa, & Indah, 2020; Riantono & Sunarto, 2022; Adaobi, 2023). Businesses can integrate environmental and social disclosure in response to this need by revealing the greenhouse gas emissions generated by their day-to-day operations. Stakeholders may view the disclosure of greenhouse gas emissions as a company response to the need to lessen the effects of environmental harm.

Board Characteristics

A board consists of a team of individuals who combine their competencies and capabilities to achieve a common purpose. They are saddled with the responsibility of initiating organizational change and facilitating the process that supports the organizational mission in an increasingly competitive environment while maintaining managerial professionalism and accountability in pursuit of good firm performance (Mbonu & Okoye, 2023). Board characteristics include board financial expertise (BFE), board gender diversity (BGEN), board independence (BIND), board meetings (BOMET), and board size (BSIZE). One of the main research questions for this study is: Does board characteristics have an impact on GHG emission disclosure?

Board Independence (BIND)

Board Independence (BIND) occurs when a board member has not been or is not currently employed by the company or its auditor and the board member's employer does not own a significant amount of business with the company (Amahalu & Osonwa, 2023). Board independence refers to outside directors who are independent of management and can closely track management actions to protect the interest of the stakeholders (Ammer et al., 2020) and also confirm that firm decisions are made in a way that protects the interests of all stakeholders (Lo, Wong, & Firth, 2010). Similarly, Khan et al., (2021) describe an independent director as a director who does not participate in the organization's day-to-day management but is involved in policy formulation and planning exercises. The role of independent directors in an organization's board has been recognized even at the policy level, with corporate governance codes emphasizing the need for a fair proportion of them on the board of an organization (Khan et al., 2021). Stakeholders' competing interests can be moderated by an independent director, according to stakeholder theory (Liao et al., 2014). Independent directors are required to uphold and defend the interests of society (Nainggolan, 2015). Therefore, it is anticipated that the possibility of GHG emission disclosure will increase with the board's level of independence as independent directors will support the disclosure of environmental data (Elmagrhi, Ntim, & Wang, 2016). It is on this basis this study formed the null hypothesis as given below:

H01: Board independence has no significant effect on the greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Board Gender Diversity (BGEN)

Diversity implies that each human is distinct and that we value our differences. Race, ethnicity, gender, sexual orientation, socioeconomic class, age, physical ability, religious beliefs, political convictions, or other ideologies can all be considered. Gender diversity refers to the equitable or fair representation of people of different genders (Cook, 2021). Gender diversity refers to the extent to which a person's gender identity, role, or expression differs from the cultural norms prescribed for people of a particular sex (Lungeanu & Zajac, 2019). Gender diversity is crucial in boards because it can contribute to board functioning, which can potentially positively influence corporate performance (Amahalu & Osonwa, 2023). BGEN is a significant aspect of corporate governance and it stems from the presence of women on boards to the percentage representation of women on corporate

boards (Mbonu & Amahalu, 2021b). According to Ahmed (2012), having women on the board would influence the board to make better decisions regarding GHG emission disclosure. In addition, the participation of female board members strengthens board oversight, which leads to better corporate governance and a strategic advantage for businesses (Marzuki et al., 2019). Pechersk (2016) points out that diversity on corporate boards adds to a greater mix of backgrounds and knowledge, creating different points of view that ensure better strategic decision-making. Hence, gender diversity became an acknowledged characteristic of board diversity (Amorelli & García-Sánchez, 2021). According to the signaling theory, which is based on the supposition of information asymmetry, having women on board communicates to minorities and women that the company values them. As a result, it conveys the idea that the business is socially conscious and takes greater initiative to disclose social actions that include GHG emission disclosure (Bear et al., 2010). It is on this basis this study formed the null hypothesis as given below:

H02: Board gender diversity has no significant effect on the greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Board Financial Expertise (BFE)

The term "board financial expertise" describes the presence of directors with relevant financial knowledge, competence, and experience on a company's board. In order to provide high-quality disclosure, financial knowledge is required. Effective corporate governance requires having directors with financial experience, particularly when it comes to monitoring financial reporting, evaluating the company's financial performance, and making well-informed financial decisions (Suleiman et al, 2023). It is impossible to overestimate the importance of board members' educational backgrounds and subject-matter knowledge in carrying out their oversight duties (Danladi, 2021). Juhmani (2017) asserts that the board of directors' efficacy in financial reporting, particularly as regards voluntary disclosure, can be enhanced by the presence of accounting and financial competence on the committee. Al Amosh & Khatib (2022) provided additional evidence in support of the idea that having a team member who is highly knowledgeable about accounting; finance, financial literacy, or financial management will improve the financial report's overall quality. It is on this basis this study formed the null hypothesis as given below:

H03: Board financial expertise has no significant effect on the GHG emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Board Size (BSIZE)

Board size refers to the total number of directors that make up an organization's management board (Okere, Rufai & Oyinloye, 2021). As a top management body, the board of directors is responsible for developing a sustainable business strategy, supervising the prudent use of the company's assets, and ensuring that material environmental risks are well-monitored and fully disclosed (Kuzey & Merve 2018). BSIZE is essential in environmental disclosure especially the GHG emission disclosure of corporate firms mainly because it will help firms make better decisions than firms with smaller BSIZE (Sharif &

Rashid 2014). Firms with larger boards would have more experts and a better result than firms with a small BSIZE because small boards tend to have fewer experts than larger ones. Larger boards are usually mixed by greater diversity, capturing different experience levels, financial expertise, and capabilities to solve problems which can boost corporate reputation and image (Ntim & Soobaroyen, 2013). Compared to firms with smaller BSIZE, entities with a larger corporate board are more likely to increase the disclosure of corporate information regarding their corporate governance (CG) practices (Al-Bassam et al., 2018). According to Jensen and Meckling (1976), agency theory is predicated on the division of ownership and control between principals and agents. Establishing a strong corporate governance framework is advised for businesses in order to save agency expenses and better align the objectives of principals and agents (Baker, 2019). Consequently, according to Buniamin et al. (2011) as well as Salehuddin and Fadzil (2013), having a sufficient number of board members may help resolve conflicts and enhance voluntary disclosures on GHG emission activities. It is on this basis this study formed the null hypothesis as given below:

H04: Board size has no significant effect on the greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Board Meetings Frequency (BOMET)

Oversight is one of the important activities in the implementation of good corporate governance (Shuaibu, Muhammed & Isah, 2019). A board meeting is a meeting of the board of directors of a corporation, typically convened at specific periods throughout the year to talk about matters about the firm as a whole. According to Olowookere, Olabisi, Oljiangbe & Olorede, (2022), the company's overarching business plan is decided by the board of directors, who are chosen by the organization's members or shareholders. The board of directors holds a meeting and the meeting takes place at regular times basically to discuss the strategic plan that has been created and also the policy concerns inside the company. According to agency theory, a board with a high frequency of meetings has a more effective function in monitoring and advising management. One crucial indicator of board activity that aids in resolving agency conflicts is the frequency of board meetings (Ofoegbu et al., 2018; Saleh et al., 2020). In assessing the impact of the board meeting on GHG emission disclosure, Koji, Adhikary and Tram (2020) express that frequent board meeting plays an important role in enhancing the disclosure performance of a company since it assists in reducing the information gap among the board members. It is on this basis this study formed the null hypothesis as given below:

H05: Board meetings frequency has no significant effect on the greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

Firm Characteristics (Control variables)

Firm characteristics refer to the attributes that a firm possesses that define its activities (Shuaibu, Ali, and Amin, 2019). These are the main influences on a firm's financial choices as well as other policies that are implemented. Variables that impact the kind, amount, and caliber of greenhouse gas emission disclosure have been documented in several research papers in the academic field. The study concentrated on the

environmental drivers, such as company size and profitability, and notable characteristics among them include the industry type, leverage, corporate governance method, and profitability.

Firm Profitability

Firm profit is the operational outcomes of a business endeavor at a specific time, achieved by an individual or group of individuals. The entirety of a business's commercial strength during a specific timeframe is referred to as profitability. It could be used to match similar businesses across related occupations or to match industries or sectors with each other for ranking to aid decision-making (Nkwoji, 2021). Therefore, a company's strength, efficacy, and proficiency in managing all of its assets to create profit are measured by its profitability. A firm's profitability is a reflection of its financial performance. Businesses that are struggling financially will devote more of their attention to making improvements and reaching their targets; as a result, they will be less able to prevent and monitor greenhouse gas emissions (Emmanuel, Doorasamy, Kwarbai, Otekunrin, & Osakede, 2024; Emmanuel, Adenikinju, Doorasamy, Ayoola, Oladejo, Kwarbai, & Otekunrin, 2023). The profitability in this study is determined by calculating the returns on assets (ROA) ratio. The reason ROA was selected is that it can be used to describe how well a company uses its assets to generate profit.

Firm Size

A firm is a for-profit, business organization such as a corporation, limited liability company, or partnership that provides professional services and also arranges for the marketing of products, provision of finance, and other facilities to run the organization (Omojolaibi, Oladipupo, & Okudo, 2019). Company size represents the company's resources, hence the larger the company, the more resources it has, and the smaller the company the fewer resources it has (Oluwamayowa, 2020). People have higher expectations of large corporations' GHG management measures. As a result, large corporations are more sensitive to transparency requirements (Freedman & Jaggi, 2005). The total value of firm assets which it owns and uses for its operations is referred to as its size. It also describes the range and amount of services that a company can offer to its customers. Economies of scale are typically used to produce these services. Thus, the firm size—which is often determined using the natural logarithm of the company's total assets—has become one of the primary factors in the majority of research investigations on company features and GHG emission disclosure.

Leverage

Financial leverage can be described as the extent to which a business or investor is using borrowed funds to finance an investment or project (Emeka, Ogochukwu & Bridget, 2021). Leverage is a measure of how much a firm uses equity and debt to finance its assets or purchase an additional asset (Hayes, 2022). As debt increases, financial leverage also increases that is, a high leverage ratio denotes a high level of financial risk for the organization.

Corporate shareholders use leverage to determine if the company has enough money to pay its present debts and whether it can make a profit from its investments. Liao et al. (2014) predict that leverage will hurt transparency

3. Theoretical Review

Various theories have been reviewed in this study; however, the study will be anchored on stakeholder theory and legitimacy theory.

Legitimacy Theory

Legitimacy theory was derived from the concept of “organizational legitimacy” and was propounded by Dowling and Pfeffer (1975). According to Lindblom (1994), legitimacy is a situation whereby a company’s set of values is non-conflicting with the ethical value of the community in which the company is just a component. Therefore, there exists a risk to the firm’s legitimacy when a disagreement is found to occur between the society’s principles and the company’s principles of being in existence. The presumption of legitimacy theory anchors on the fact that only firms that align their operations with the norms and values of society can continue to be in operation and survive (Ezhilarasi & Kabra 2017). Legitimacy theory depends on the belief in a social agreement between the firm and the society in which the company operates (Azzam, Alqudah, Haija & Shakhatreh, 2021). Consequently, corporate entities are to carry out their business operations in alignment with the society’s ethical boundaries and values and ensure their environmental performances are disclosed in the annual reports for stakeholders to see their existence in the society as legitimate (Nwachukwu, Ogundiwin & Nwaobia, 2015). The advocates of the theory state that firms should voluntarily disclose information and its corporate governance structure because voluntary disclosure legitimizes firms’ business activities and improves their reputation (Pattern 1992; Hurst 1970; Deegan, 1996; Gray, 1995; Clarke, 1996; Adams & Roberts, 1995). Also, posited that management should reveal sufficient information to protect their integrity, and interest, stimulate and legitimize associations. It for the reasons aforementioned that this study adopts Legitimacy theory

Stakeholder Theory

The term “stakeholder theory” was propounded by Edward Freeman (1984). A stakeholder is historically called “any community or person who may have an impact or influence on the attainment of the organization’s objectives” (Freeman 1984). The stakeholders’ concept is an explainable theory for reporting social and environmental matters (Ofoegbu, Odoemelam, & Okafor, 2018). According to Freeman (2004) stakeholder theory encompasses “all groups that are vital to the organization’s existence and success” and is also a theory of organizational management and business ethics that address the morals and values in managing an organization, such as those related to corporate social responsibility, market economy, and social contract theory (Lin et al. 2018). The advocate of the theory state that a company is not an entity that operates for its own business only but it should provide benefits and create value to its stakeholders such as customers, suppliers, employees, government, community, environment, lenders and future generation (Rissy,2021). Deegan and Unerman, (2008) suggests that instead of a single social

contract with the society, an organization is bound to different social contracts to each stakeholder and this is because every stakeholder has different perspectives as regards the organization's activities.

Stakeholder Management is central to the organization corporate existence regardless of the firm's intent; a successful firm can handle the relationships that are essential to the firm's corporate existence (Harrison, 2021). The corporation must adjust more as the power of the stakeholder's increases. According to Wang and Yang (2020), stakeholders should be given pertinent information, particularly environmental information, and have adequate access to certain information for particular decisions. Some stakeholders have the ability to influence or control corporate resources. The degree of influence they have over the resources helps to understand their power. This theory maintains that there is a need for an organization to be actively involved in the society where it operates since it depends on the society for sustenance (Ojo, 2012). One of the community's interests in the company is the company's concern for the environment. The corporation will communicate the information through a channel known as GHG emission disclosure to gain legitimacy and maintain its legitimacy according to stakeholder needs (Liu & Yang, 2018). The strengths of stakeholders will improve environmental reporting (Yanto & Halimah, 2018). Thus, it can be concluded that the stakeholders' theory, emphasizes the company to have a responsibility to the environment.

Agency Theory

Agency theory was propounded by Jensen & Meckling (1976). The interaction involving the principal and the agent is delineated by agency theory. Agency theory recognizes that there is a tug-of-war between owners or principals and managers (Kleiman, 2011). The agency problem arises from the separation of control and ownership, which leaves investors or stockholders and corporate managers with different levels of understanding and exposure to information. In line with agency theory, information disclosure is a way of mitigating conflict of interest between shareholders and corporate managers and to avoid conflicts of interest, the principal can establish a monitoring system through which managers are disciplined to act in their interest (Bushman & Smith, 2001). Many firm' strategies have been implemented over time to reduce the conflict of interest brought about by agency relationships and deal with the issue of information asymmetry. A regard to this, the Board represents a monitoring mechanism aimed at balancing the interest of management and shareholders about both financial information and non-financial information like environmental disclosure (Bushman & Smith, 2001; Prado-Lorenzo & Garcia-Sanchez, 2010). Hence, board monitoring entails lowering information asymmetry between agents and principals and the related agency problems while simultaneously encouraging the release of high-quality information from firms.

Signaling Theory

Signaling theory was propounded by Michael Spence (1973). The problematic nature of information skewness is explained by the Signaling theory. When investors and firm management have access to different amounts of knowledge, information asymmetry becomes a problem (Healy & Palepu, 2001). Thus, reducing knowledge asymmetry is the

primary objective of information disclosure. According to signaling theory, businesses reveal to demonstrate their success, set themselves apart from the public, and lessen information asymmetry, increasing their standing and public opinion (Joseph & Godwin, 2016). This notion demonstrates that society precisely evaluates the accuracy of a signal by analyzing the signal; hence signal sent to society is a credible disclosure of a firm's effort to regulate its relationship with the environment (Cho et al., 2015).

According to Omran and El-Galfy (2014), insiders would protect themselves by giving a cheaper price because they are better knowledgeable than investors about a firm and its prospects. However, if the business willingly discloses (signals) personal information about itself that is reliable and lowers outsider uncertainty, the company's worth may improve (Mahoney, 2012). Although the information asymmetry in the labor market was the main focus of the signaling theory, it has also been applied to explain voluntary disclosure in corporate reporting. Due to the information asymmetry issue, corporations communicate to investors that they have stronger corporate social responsibility practices than other businesses in the market to attract investments and boost a positive reputation (Ogunrinde, 2018).

Signaling theory states that voluntary disclosure of non-financial information, such proprietary knowledge, should tell investors of good news and increase a firm's worth. Signaling theory suggests that firms with superior quality are more likely to inform the market of their competitive advantage. Companies are incentivized to divulge confidential information without restraint, as it is perceived as an indication of robust operations and a decrease in information asymmetry. Positive recognition and contact with potential investors are the outcomes (Kurnia et al., 2020). If a business voluntarily and thoroughly discloses its greenhouse gas emissions, it has a greater chance of benefiting from increased share prices. Furthermore, the stock market might deter firms that don't disclose and see non-disclosure behavior as a bad sign (Liu et al., 2017).

4. Methodology

Ex-post facto research design was employed in this study as it involves panel data and this was chosen because the study makes use of recorded events and the recorder does not have control over the variables under study and therefore cannot be manipulated (Asogwa, Ugwuanyi, & Anumudu, 2018). The population of the study comprises of 34 manufacturing firms operating in the industrial and consumer goods sectors as listed on the Nigeria Exchange group from 2012-2021. The population of the study was chosen because manufacturing firms is one of the significant sources of GHG emission. Purposive Sampling Technique was adopted to select the firms with up-to-date annual report and sustainability reports for the study period. Secondary data for GHG emission disclosure, board characteristics and firm characteristics (control variables) were obtained from the 2012–2021 annual reports and sustainability reports of the listed Nigerian manufacturing firms. To achieve the research objectives of the study descriptive and inferential statistics was employed. The study hypotheses were analyzed using inferential Statistics. Inferential statistics was used to analyze the data quality (Classical assumption test) and hypotheses testing (Multiple Regression analysis). The classical assumption test consist of normality

test (Shapiro-Wilk test) to test whether the residual values is distributed normally, Multicollinearity test (Variance inflation factor) to test whether there is any correlation between independent variables and Heteroscedasticity testing (Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test) to examine whether the residual value in the model are unequal.

Model Specification

In Order to test for the relevance of the hypotheses regarding the effect of board characteristics on GHG emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria. This study adapted the model of Astuti and Setiany (2021)

Considering the utilization of the adapted model, the model was thus formulated as follows:

$$GHGED_{it} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 BIND_{it} + \beta_2 BGEN_{it} + \beta_3 BSIZE_{it} + \beta_4 BOMET_{it} + \beta_5 BFE_{it} + \beta_6 ROA_{it} + \beta_7 SIZE_{it} + \beta_8 LEV_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \dots \dots \dots \text{Model 1}$$

Where:

α = Intercept of the regression

B1-8= Regression coefficient

GHGED = greenhouse gas emission disclosure of Firm i in period t

BSIZE= Board Size = Total numbers of the company's management

BIND= Board Independence == Number of Non- Executive Directors / Number of Directors

BGEN= Board Gender Diversity = = Number of Female Directors / Number of Directors

BOMET= Board Meetings = the total number of meetings held by the board of a firm

BFE= Board Financial Expertise = Total numbers of directors on the board with financial expertise

SIZE = Size of Firm = Natural Logarithm of total assets

ROA= Profitability of Firm = Net Profit / Total Assets

LEV= Leverage of Firm = Total debts/total sum of assets

ϵ = error term

A- Priori Expectations

The independent and dependent variables have both positive and negative connections established by prior research. The researcher anticipates that the disclosure of greenhouse gas emissions of listed manufacturing firms will be significantly impacted by board attributes and A- Priori Expectations as given below:

Table 1

Variable	Parameter	Expectation
Board Independence	β_1	$\beta_1 > 0$
Board Gender Diversity	β_2	$\beta_2 > 0$
Board Size	β_3	$\beta_3 > 0$
Board Meetings	β_4	$\beta_4 > 0$
Board Financial Expertise	β_5	$\beta_5 > 0$

Source: Researcher Compilation 2023

5. Result and Discussion Of Findings

Correlation Analysis

The Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient (correlation matrix) (Table 2) was utilized in the study to investigate the relationship between the series. The findings are shown in the table below. The association between the explanatory series, study-used control series, and GHG emission disclosure is displayed in the table below. In particular, the data demonstrates that over the study time frame, there is a positive correlation between BIND (0.160) and the dependent series of GHG emission disclosure. Additionally, the outcome demonstrates a positive correlation between the dependent series which is GHG emission disclosure throughout the study timeframe and BGEN (0.179). Additionally, during the study time frame, there is a positive correlation between BSIZE (0.416) and the dependent series of GHG emission disclosure. During the study time frame, there is a positive correlation between the dependent series of GHG emission disclosure and board meetings (0.348). Additionally, there is a positive correlation between the dependent series of GHG emission disclosure during the study timeframe and BFE (0.494). Additionally, the outcome demonstrates a positive correlation between the dependent series of GHG emission disclosure within the study timeframe and return on asset (0.176). Additionally, there is a positive correlation between firm size (528) and the dependent series of GHG emission disclosure across the study timeframe. Nonetheless, the outcome demonstrates that leverage (-0.122) has a negative correlation with the dependent series of disclosure of greenhouse gas emissions across the study timeframe. Regression findings will be required to test the hypotheses, though, as a correlation test is unable to identify a cause-and-effect link.

Table 2 Correlation Analysis

Variable	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
1. GHGED	1.000								
2. BIND	0.160	1.000							
3. BGEN	0.179	-0.021	1.000						
4. B SIZE	0.416	0.110	-0.034	1.000					
5. BOMET	0.348	0.027	0.323	0.302	1.000				
6. BFE	0.494	0.244	0.185	0.556	0.352	1.000			
7. SIZE	0.176	-0.109	0.205	-0.018	0.242	0.099	1.000		
8. ROA	0.528	0.066	0.189	0.697	0.318	0.528	0.243	1.000	
9. LEV	-0.122	-0.137	-0.111	-0.144	-0.232	-0.249	-0.437	-0.179	1.000

Source: Researchers Compilation, 2024

Regression Analysis

Specifically, the study starts by estimating the pool OLS regression (Table 3) and tests for the basic assumptions of the pool OLS regression. The diagnostic test includes multicollinearity and homoscedasticity. The table that follows displays the multivariate regression analysis outcome. For the dependent series of GHG emission disclosure, the pool OLS regression got an R-squared value of 0.3699, according to the results. This suggests that roughly 37% of the systematic variations in the dependent series of GHG emission disclosure of the collection of manufacturing companies across the study years may be explained by the various independent series of the research. Nonetheless, the error term has accounted for the portion of the GHG emission disclosure that cannot be explained. The pool OLS regression model is generally statistically fit at a 1% level of significance and can be used for statistical inferences, according to the F-statistics of the models for the sample manufacturing enterprises in Nigeria and the corresponding p-value of 0.0000. Nevertheless, this work includes tests for heteroscedasticity and multicollinearity to additionally validate the estimations of the pool OLS results.

Table 3: OLS Regression Results

	GHGED (Pool OLS)	GHGED (Fixed Effect)	GHGED (Random Effect)
CONS.	-0.613 {0.000} ***	-0.951 {0.015} **	-0.740 {0.000} ***
BIND	0.002 {0.095}	0.002 {0.037} **	0.002 {0.018} **
BGEN	0.002 {0.055}	0.004 {0.001} **	0.004 {0.000} ***
BFE	0.028 {0.000} ***	0.020 {0.007} **	0.023 {0.001} **
B SIZE	0.010 {0.078}	0.011 {0.077}	0.011 {0.063}
BOMET	0.019 {0.077}	0.013 {0.157}	0.014 {0.122}
ROA	-0.000 {0.821}	-0.001 {0.435}	-0.001 {0.424}
SIZE	0.049 {0.005} **	0.092 {0.101}	0.062 {0.030} **
LEV	6.890 {0.990}	0.000 {0.708}	0.000 {0.749}
F-Stat.	18/93 {0.0000}	9.02 {0.0000}	91.13 {0.0000}
R- Squared	0.3699	0.2372	0.2360
Hausman			3.27 {0.0716}

Source: Researcher Compilation

Note: (1) bracket {} are p-values;

(2) **, ***, implies statistical Significance at 5% and 1% respectively.

Test for Multicollinearity

Multicollinearity in regression analysis as in Table 4 occurs when two or more highly correlated explanatory variables. They don't offer the regression model any special or

independent data. It could be challenging to fit and understand the regression model if there is a sufficiently significant connection between the series. The variance inflation factor (VIF), which is the reciprocal of tolerance, is mostly used to identify multicollinearity. As can be seen from Table 4, the result reveals that there is no multicollinearity and that none of the independent series needs to be removed from the model, since the mean VIF is 1.62.

Table 4: Variance Inflation Factor (VIF)

Variable	VIF	1/VIF
B SIZE	2.37	0.421
BOMET	1.28	0.984
BIND	1.12	0.895
BGEN	1.21	0.828
BFE	1.74	0.575
LEV	1.47	0.681
ROA	1.46	0.687
SIZE	2.33	0.429
Mean VIF	1.62	

Source: Researchers Compilation, 2024

Test for Heteroscedasticity

It will be challenging to accept the standard errors of the least square estimates if the errors are heteroscedastic, according to the homoscedasticity assumption. As a result, the confidence intervals will be excessively large or narrow. The result as in Table 5 shows a p-value of 0.0000 for the regression model. The result implies significant p-values indicating that the assumption of homoscedasticity of the pool OLS regression results has been violated. Hence, the study re-specifies the model to control for this violation by employing the panel regression as recommended by Greene, (2003)

Table 5 Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for Heteroscedasticity

Breusch-Pagan / Cook-Weisberg test for heteroscedasticity

Ho: Constant variance

Variables: Fitted Values of GHGED

chi2(7) = 80.91

Prob > chi2 = 0.0000

Source: Researcher's compilation, 2024

Panel Fixed and Random Effects

Specifically, in this study as in Table 6, the F-statistic and Wald-statistic values of 9.02 (0.0000) and 91.13 (0.0000) for fixed and random effect regression respectively show that both models are valid for drawing inference since they are statistically significant at 1%. In the case of the coefficient of determination (R-squared), it was observed that less of the changes in the GHG emission disclosure as a result of the interest rate used in this study is explained using both the random and fixed effect (27%) than the OLS regression (37%). The random effect model is chosen above the fixed effect model, according to the null hypothesis of the Hausman test, which was performed while opting based on the two-panel regression estimation results. In particular, the Hausman test's p-value of 0.9162 suggests

that, at significance levels over 5% or 1%, we reject the alternative and accept the null hypothesis. This suggests that the study's conclusions and suggestions should be based on the findings of the random effect panel regression. This suggests that statistically speaking; the random effect results are typically more attractive than the fixed effect. In light of the aforementioned, it became essential to discuss the random effect outcomes to test the hypothesis.

Hypotheses

H01: Board independence has no significant effect on the greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria

The result of the random effect regression as presented in table 4.7 shows that BINDS {coeff. = 0.002, $p= 0.018$ } has a positive significant effect on the GHG emission disclosure. Hence, the null hypothesis that BIND has no significant effect on GHG emission disclosure is rejected and the alternative hypothesis that BIND has significant effect on GHG emission disclosure is accepted.

H02: Board gender diversity has no significant effect on the greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria

BGEN {coeff. = 0.004, $p= 0.000$ } has a positive significant effect on the GHG emission disclosure. Hence, the null hypothesis that BGEN has no significant effect on GHG emission disclosure is rejected and the alternative hypothesis that BGEN has significant effect on GHG emission disclosure is accepted.

H03: Board financial expertise has no significant effect on the greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria

BFE {coeff = 0.023, $p= 0.001$ } has a positive significant effect on the GHG emission disclosure. Hence, the null hypothesis that BFE has no significant effect on GHG emission disclosure is rejected and the alternative hypothesis that BFE has significant effect on GHG emission disclosure is accepted.

H04: Board size has no significant effect on the greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

BSIZE {coeff = 0.011, $p= 0.063$ } has positive insignificant effects on GHG emission disclosure. Hence, the null hypothesis that BSIZE has no significant effect on GHG emission disclosure is accepted and the alternative hypothesis that BSIZE has significant effect on GHG emission disclosure is rejected.

H05: Board meetings frequency has no significant effect on the greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria.

BOMET {coeff = 0.014, $p= 0.122$ } has positive insignificant effects on GHG emission disclosure. Hence, the null hypothesis that BOMET has no significant effect on GHG emission disclosure is accepted and the alternative hypothesis that BOMET significant effect on GHG emission disclosure is rejected.

The result of the random effect regression as presented in Table 6 shows that firm characteristics when measured in terms of firm size {coeff. = 0.062, $p= 0.030$ } has a positive significant effect on the GHG emission disclosure. This result implies that an increase in firm size will significantly increase the disclosure of GHG emission. In terms of leverage, the result shows that leverage {coeff. = 0.000, $p=0.749$ } has a positive insignificant effect on the GHG emission disclosure. This result implies that that an increase in leverage will insignificantly increase the disclosure of GHG emission. Return on asset {coeff. = -0.001, $p= 0.424$ } has a negative insignificant effect on the GHG emission disclosure. This result shows that an increase in return on assets will insignificantly decrease the disclosure of GHG emission.

Table 6: Random effect regression Results

Dependent Variable: GHGED				
Variables	Coeff	S.E	z-test	Prob
Constant	-0.740	0.202	-0.366	0.000
BIND	0.002	0.001	2.370	0.018
BGEN	0.004	0.001	3.640	0.000
B SIZE	0.107	0.057	1.860	0.063
BOMET	0.014	0.009	1.550	0.122
BFE	0.227	0.007	3.260	0.001
SIZE	0.062	0.028	2.17	0.030
ROA	-0.001	0.001	-0.080	0.424
LEV	0.002	0.005	0.32	0.749
	Statistic	Prob		
R- Squared	0.3605			
F-test	91.130	0.0000		

Discussion of findings on hypothesis:

This study examined the relationship between board characteristics and greenhouse gas emission disclosure. Proxies used for firm board characteristics include BFE, BGEN, BIND, BOMET, and BSIZE. The regression analysis result above indicates BFE, BGEN and BIND has significant positive effect greenhouse gas emission disclosure. Hence, this study result implies that BIND increases, greenhouse gas emission disclosure also increases. This result is in line with earlier research (Biswas et al., 2018; Saraswati, Puspita, & Sagitaputri, 2021). Based on the result it means independent directors can step up their oversight of the management and promote greater management transparency.

Also, the regression analysis result shows that as BGEN increases, greenhouse gas emission disclosure also increases. Additionally, gender diversity on boards has a positive impact on greenhouse gas emission disclosures, as indicated by the regression result. This study result is in line with earlier research (Hollindale et al., 2019). According to this study, female directors make decisions that are more morally, strategically, and risk-averse. The finding of H01 and H02 supported legitimacy and stakeholder theories, that firms create social contracts with stakeholders in accordance with the legitimacy and stakeholder theories. Different viewpoints and expectations may be held by such stakeholders towards the organization. It is anticipated that a board that is more diverse and independent will be better able to resolve stakeholder conflicts (Saraswati, Puspita, & Sagitaputri, 2021). The regression analysis result also shows that as board financial expertise increases,

greenhouse gas emission disclosure also increases. However, BSIZE and BOMET has no effects on GHG emission disclosure. The regression analysis result above indicates BSIZE, and BOMET has no significant positive effect greenhouse gas emission disclosure.

6. Conclusion and Recommendations

This study examined the effect of board characteristics on greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2012 to 2021. The specific purposes of the study were to determine the trend of greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria, assess the effect of board characteristics on greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing in Nigeria. Findings show that the board independence, board gender diversity, and board financial expertise significantly influence the greenhouse gas emission disclosure made by manufacturing firms in Nigeria. It was revealed that board financial expertise, board gender diversity and board independence has a positive and significant effect on greenhouse gas emission disclosure which indicate that an increase in non-executive directors, female directors, and number of board members with financial expertise will significantly increase the disclosure of greenhouse gas emission activities of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria during the period under study. Board size and board meetings do not significantly affect the disclosure the greenhouse gas emission made by manufacturing firms but they were positively related to greenhouse gas emission disclosure. Hence, this study concluded that board characteristics have effect on greenhouse gas emission disclosure of listed manufacturing firms in Nigeria from 2012 to 2021.

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